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Abstracts

Theme 2B: Quality Infrastructure and Leadership (QIL) (More focus on ICT)

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1. Web based software as a facilitator of quality management of ODL Institutes

Dr. Mushtaq Ahmed I Patel, Associate Professor in Education, DDE, MANUU,
Hyderabad patel_mushtaq@hotmail.com

Ms. Mohasina Anjum A. Ansari, Research Assistant, CSSEIP, MANUU, Hyderabad
patel_mushtaq@hotmail.com

Educational institutions all over the globe are adopting online for quality management of programmes, as a result of availability of improved bandwidth, lower cost of telecommunication network and potential pedagogical benefits. Researchers have proved that the web based software help in proper management of learner data, immediate correction of information, better liaison between different stakeholders of educational institutes; greater access of information (anytime-anywhere learning). The Internet is a huge resource for performing all sorts of educational transactions in Open Distance Learning (ODL). The new millennium has witnessed an unprecedented diffusion of network technologies into educational institutes. ODL institutes today need to concentrate on management of their data and information for efficiency and effectiveness. Web-based software allows accurate and timely use of information to reduce the common problems of management of ODL institutes. The major gains by use of such an ICT services are in the form of improving quality, reduction of teaching and time cost, complementing the efforts of Human Resources and promoting interaction.

The Open and Distance Learning institutes are playing a vital role is propagation of knowledge and enhancing literacy levels. The ODL as a system is a boon to many like all house holds, dropouts and professionals, persons with responsibility of family etc. This has reduced wastage of time and resources with regard to transport and provides flexibility in admission, study and exam. The learners have facility for choices of programmes, self-paced learning. The academic counsellors have to meet the demands of these learners in ODL system. This system at the same line has certain barriers like non-availability of faculty, organisational barriers etc. The maintenance, storage and transfer of data and provision of learner support services to such a large group of learners are an important aspect. All these require maintenance of huge amount of information. The web based software can be developed so that the data can be recorded, stored, transferred and reports can be generated at different levels in ODL systems. The online resources are also useful for learners in tracking their admission, supply of books, getting feedback for assignments, latest developments etc. These concerns can only be met through well designed web-based software.

The present paper attempts to study the web based software being developed at MANUU as a facilitator of quality enhancement with regard to ODL. This paper is intended to know what a web-based software is, role of web-based software in quality management of ODL programme, quality indicators for web-based software, issues and concerns of development of web-based software for ODL system, challenges of development of web-based software.